

Paste your Photograph Here

Paste your Logo here

Title: Risk Analysis of Self-Driving Force

Name: Calvenn Tsuu

Affiliation: Talented Component Co. Ltd, AB T3H3B9, CANADA

INTRODUCTION:

We love automation. We love to predict the future. We can use logic to predict, or use gut feeling to predict. Logic may based on the knowledge we have learned in our life. But the gut feeling may based on the experiences in our life as well. We may emphasize the logic and formulas over other a lot. The current progress in artificial neural network deep learning can prove there is another way of learning and predicting.

AIM:

To graphically evaluate the risk of rising computing power with unmatched public education about self-driving forces.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A prospective study was conducted in Calgary over a eleven months period in which a total of 14 projects were completed in order to evaluate the confidences of each concept on self-driving car development. It covers machine vision, detection, prediction, plan and controls. We were using robotic approach and deep learning approach.

RESULTS:

In every project, machine can reach near or better than human performance. For robotic approached projects, such as lane detection, sensor fusion, path planning and closed loop control systems, we were manually tuned all parameters. It is possible to achieve better results using automatic tuning methods. For deep learning approach projects, such as behavior cloning, vehicle detection, semantic segmentation and system integration, we provided enough data for machine to learn human tasks, all based on supervised learning method. Machine can reach 97% accuracy on training set and test set, the real performance are acceptable by the project specification and human eyes.

CONCLUSIONS:

As a whole, we still have lot of room to improve.....

KEYWORDS:

Risk Analysis; Deep Learning; Neural Network; Robotic Approach; Parameter Tuning

BIOGRAPHY:

Calvonn Tsuu is a former Project Controls Engineer, former Mechanical Engineer and current huge fan of all things data. Calvonn has been working with planning and scheduling on mega projects for past 8 years. Part of his work used Monte Carlo Model to evaluate project completion risk. This is where he fell in love with data. He presented a technical paper in ACEi annual meeting about his findings. He is fascinated by the new progress in deep learning machine can achieve higher performance than human. He is passion about make integrated robot system to improve our life experiences.